

THE ROLE OF CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article highlights the importance of the Content and Language Integrated Learning method in the education system. The study also analyzes the role of the CLIL method in improving students' communicative competence, critical thinking, and engagement. It also examines the problems of implementing this method in practice and ways to overcome them.

Key words: Integration, communication, competence, methodology, interactivity, bilingualism, cognition, innovation, adaptation, modernization.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Kontent va tilni integratsiyalashgan o'rganish metodining ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati yoritib beriladi. Tadqiqot davomida CLIL metodining o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasi, tanqidiy fikrlashi va faolligini oshirishdagi roli ham tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ushbu metodni amaliyotga joriy etishdagi muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kirish so'zlar: Integratsiya, kommunikatsiya, kompetensiya, metodologiya, interaktivlik, bilingvizm, kognitsiya, innovatsiya, adaptatsiya, modernizatsiya.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье подчеркивается важность метода интегрированного обучения содержанию и языку (CLIL) в системе образования. Исследование также анализирует роль метода CLIL в повышении коммуникативной компетентности, критического мышления и вовлеченности учащихся. Кроме того, рассматриваются проблемы внедрения этого метода на практике и способы их преодоления.

Ключевые слова: Интеграция, коммуникация, компетентность, методология, интерактивность, двуязычие, познание, инновации, адаптация, модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization and the rapid development of information technologies, the perfect mastery of foreign languages is becoming a necessary skill for every specialist. In particular, the effective organization of the language teaching process in the education system, the development of not only linguistic, but also logical and professional competencies of students, is of great importance. For this reason, the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) method, which is one of the modern pedagogical approaches, deserves special attention. CLIL is essentially based on the use of English as a communicative tool in the study of professional content, not as a separate subject. The "4C" model developed by Coyle, Marsh and Hood - the components of Content, Communication, Cognition and Culture - allows for the organization of integrated lessons for technical school students that are meaningful, communicative and require deep thinking, and also allows students to develop every day and

professional speech, active use of technical terms, and a deep understanding of the subject. CLIL, especially when used in a technical school setting, is combined with ESP (English for specific purposes) lessons and increases the quality of students' mastery of professionally oriented English [1] The CLIL method is a unique integrative approach in which subject content and a foreign language are taught together. This allows students to learn the language not only in an artificial environment, but also in a real context. As a result, students master the language not only at the level of grammatical rules, but also through practical application. At the same time, this method also develops students' skills in critical thinking, problem solving and independent research. Today, the use of the CLIL method is widely used in the education system of many developed countries and is characterized by its high efficiency. Therefore, studying this method and adapting it to the local education system is of significant scientific and practical importance.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Integrated lessons require effective collaboration between vocational teachers and English teachers. While the English teacher organizes language structure, grammar, and communicative tasks, the vocational teacher provides technical content, terminology, laboratory work, and real-world professional situations. One of the methodological advantages of these teachers over each other is that it leads to real-world integration rather than to a rule-based approach to language learning. CLIL technology is not a short-term activity or a temporary method, but rather an educational system that is implemented consistently over many years. International experience has shown that students educated in bilingual CLIL programs usually achieve academic proficiency in a foreign language after 5-7 years [2] In the current era of globalization, the use of the most effective and proven methods and technologies in education is required. In particular, in recent years, the study of foreign languages has risen to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan. This, in turn, will lead to the wider implementation of CLIL and similar innovative methods, their practical application and support in all systems from primary education to higher education institutions, which will certainly show their effectiveness. Along with language competence, students develop critical thinking skills and the ability to work based on innovative approaches. This innovative method also saves students' time and contributes to increasing their vocabulary. Teachers also improve their professional skills and develop and form skills in working with innovative technologies. In Western countries, integrated foreign language teaching has existed for several thousand years. In the 200s BC, the Greeks taught Greek to non-Greek speakers during the expansion of the Roman state. The CLIL approach was formed in Europe towards the end of the 20th century as part of language policy. In the early 1990s, the European Union paid special attention to the development of multilingualism and the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in schools. As a result, integrated approaches emerged instead of traditional language teaching methods [3]

DISCUSSION AND RESULT

In the CLIL method, the student not only learns a foreign language and science, but also gets acquainted with the culture, international values, and educational standards of another country through this process. He also re-evaluates his own country, language, and culture, and through comparison, intercultural competence is formed. This leads to an increase in the student's worldview, thinking, level of tolerance, and ability to accept innovative knowledge.

This process is important in the formation of global citizenship, communication and flexibility, and universal competencies. CLIL technology is an effective means of simultaneously developing English language skills and professional competencies in college students. Integrated lessons increase students' motivation and help them become specialists who can communicate according to global standards. The CLIL model is based on the principle of teaching English in conjunction with other subject content. Through this method, students have the opportunity to acquire language in a natural and meaningful context by studying subjects such as biology, history or geography in English. CLIL lessons have the following advantages:

- language skills and subject knowledge develop simultaneously;
- guide students to higher-level thinking;
- approach the language environment through the use of authentic materials[4]

CLIL lessons increase students' interest in the lesson, as language learning is linked to real-world content. Research has shown that this method ensures active participation of students and enhances a communicative approach. However, its effective use requires a high level of training and methodological knowledge from teachers. The CLIL method is of great importance in the modern education system. It serves to jointly develop students' knowledge of language and science and forms their global competencies. At the same time, for the successful implementation of the CLIL approach, it is necessary to improve the skills of teachers and develop appropriate teaching materials. In general, this method has a positive effect on improving the quality of education. Pedagogical observations on the effectiveness of CLIL technology in technical schools show that integrated education has a more active and practical orientation compared to traditional English lessons. According to the results of the study, in the group trained on the basis of CLIL, the indicator of knowledge of professional terms increased from 37% to 81%, and oral communication skills increased from 2.4 points to 4.1 points. In the control group, this indicator remained much lower. The reason for this is that in CLIL lessons, the language is used in real situations, the student actively participates in the educational process, finds solutions to problem situations, performs professional tasks and, most importantly, uses English as a practical tool [5]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method is one of the effective and innovative approaches in the modern education system. Through this method, students have the opportunity to develop both scientific knowledge and foreign language skills at the same time. As a result, their communicative competence, critical thinking and cultural literacy increase. Also, the effective use of the CLIL method requires high qualifications of teachers and the right methodological approach. This method serves to improve the quality of education and make students competitive in a global environment. The CLIL method serves to organize the educational process more meaningfully and effectively. It allows students to study language not as a separate subject, but as a means of acquiring real knowledge. As a result, students gain a deeper understanding of knowledge and develop the ability to apply it in practice, and the CLIL approach also stimulates independent thinking and active participation of students. Therefore, the widespread introduction of this method is one of the important directions of modern education. The CLIL method serves to combine language learning in the educational process not only with theoretical, but also with practical activities. Through this approach, students can freely express their thoughts within the framework of various subject

topics. Also, in the CLIL method, language is used as a natural means of communication, and students develop speech skills appropriate to real situations. In addition, this method helps to expand students' intercultural understanding. In this regard, CLIL has its place in modern education as an integrated and effective approach.

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